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Success cases from BEACONING

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABR	DESCRIPTION
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LA	Learning Analytics
R&D	Research and Development
VET	Vocational Education and Training

1 INTRODUCTION

Following the requirements identified by the reviewers in the project review, this document describes the success cases carried out by partners in the different countries. The goal of this document is to distribute the cases carried out to share the actions taken and the lessons learned to provide examples that can be replicated from other partners in different countries or contexts, or to provide different ideas for dissemination contributions in the final months of the project.

The success cases identified so far cover seven countries (Spain, France, Romania, Portugal, UK, Italy, Turkey) and an additional case that covered many cities in Europe (the cross-european location-based event).

The present document will later be added as an appendix of the deliverable *D2.4 - Dissemination results 2* of the project as part of *WP2 – Dissemination and Communication*.

1.1 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The document is structured as follows:

Section 2 describes the BEACONING Game Learning Analytics best practice example for Spain by UCM.

Section 3 describes the BEACONING best practice example for France by ORT.

Section 4 describes the BEACONING best practice example for Romania by SIVECO.

Section 5 describes the BEACONING Game Authoring Tool best practice example for Portugal by INESC TEC.

Section 6 describe the BEACONING best practice example for UK by HWU.

Section 7 describes the BEACONING best practice examples and for UK by COVUNI.

Section 8 and Section 9 describe the BEACONING best practice examples for Italy by Imaginary.

Section 10 and Section 11 describe further best practice examples for France by ORT.

Section 12 describes the best practice example for Turkey by Sebit.

Section 13 describes the Cross European Location-Based event by Geomotion Games.

Section 14 describes another case for UK by COVUNI.

2 GAME LEARNING ANALYTICS BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE SPAIN (UCM)

2.1 ACTIVITY

This activity consists of a set of experiments in schools with teachers to promote the adoption of serious games and to test the acceptability of the resulting analytics dashboards while students play a serious game in class. These experiments also provide information on the applicability and perception of games as an educational tool to promote discussion and reflection in the classroom.

2.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

BEACONING Game Learning Analytics:

BEACONING analytics have been used with *Conectado*, a serious game to raise awareness about cyberbullying in schools. The game has been developed by the Telefonica-Complutense Chair on Serious Games at UCM. The choice of game was driven by the high interest on this subject from schools and educational authorities in Spain.

2.3 STAKEHOLDERS

The main stakeholders involved in the activity are schools, teachers, educational sciences students and educational authorities.

2.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

We have contacted INTEF¹ (*Instituto Nacional de Tecnologías Educativas y de Formación del Profesorado*), part of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport of Spain; and the Madrid Regional Government educational authorities. A regional education association in Madrid² has also been contacted for increased exposure.

Outreach collaboration agreements have also been established with the Telefónica-Complutense Chair on Serious Games, with the regional Network of Excellence in e-learning eMadrid, and with the H2020 RAGE project.

The goal is to reach at least a total of 10 schools totaling over 100 teachers, and 2 universities with at least 100 students of educational sciences. As of this writing (November 2017) 2 schools with a total of 28 teachers have participated in tests examining the perception and applicability of the game. Previously, initial validation experiments of the game with 257 students from 3 schools (located in Madrid, Zaragoza and Teruel) were carried out, validating the game itself and basic analytics collection.

Several schools and teachers have already been contacted for future experiments: as of November 2017, 4 schools have confirmed their participation. Also, students of the final year of the degree in educational sciences at UCM have agreed to participate in early December 2017.

Currently (April 2018), the experiments have been conducted with a total of 60 teachers, 106 educational students and 416 students, in Madrid, Murcia, Zaragoza and Teruel.

¹ <http://educalab.es/intef>

² <http://orientacionyeducacion.es/>

2.5 CONTEXT

This activity focuses on the Learning Analytics (LA) framework for use by teachers. The main goals of this activity are to:

1. Increase the adoption of games in schools
2. Involve teachers in the application of games in schools
3. Analyze the use and acceptability by teachers of the analytics dashboards

As the BEACONING Analytics System is general, results are applicable to both BEACONING and non-project games.

2.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

The original game validation experiments gained significant coverage in the media, including:

- Television:
 - o <http://www.rtve.es/alacarta/videos/telediario/telediario-15-horas-15-05-17/4020638/> (National Spanish television)
 - o <http://www.telemadrid.es/programas/telenoticias-1/telenoticias-1-11052017> (Madrid Region television)
- Journal and media websites:
 - o <http://www.efeescuela.es/noticias/escolares-la-piel-una-victima-ciberacoso/>
 - o http://www.abc.es/familia/educacion/abci-receta-contr-obesidad-infantil-menos-plato-mas-zapato-y-videojuegos-201705112222_noticia.html
 - o <http://meristation.as.com/noticias/el-videojuego-que-busca-concienciar-sobre-el-%E2%80%98bullying%E2%80%99/2243097>
 - o <http://ecodiario.economista.es/sociedad/noticias/8738032/11/17/Preparan-un-videojuego-que-hace->
 - o <http://www.servimedia.es/Noticias/Detalle.aspx?n=746919>
- Publications on the original game validation experiments:
 - o <http://dimglobal.net/revistaDIM36/revistanewbuenaspracticashtm#ciberbullying>
 - o http://www.e-ucm.es/drafts/e-UCM_draft_320.pdf (Master Thesis)

2.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

To be reproduced in a different country or context, the game to be used should be integrated with the BEACONING Analytics System. As stated above, the game used has been developed by the Telefonica-Complutense chair on Serious Games, and is so far only available in Spanish. The topic addressed by the game should be of interest to schools and educational authorities.

Beyond that, BEACONING Analytics could be used in any other country / context. Dashboards could require a minimum configuration to the local language. In the previous experiments in Spain, labels in visualizations were written in English.

2.8 OTHER INFORMATION

The experiments are built on top of a previous experience for LA validation at UCM using the game *DownTown*. These experiments were carried out after incorporating the initial version of the BEACONING LA system to a previously created game (produced by Francisco de Vitoria University at Madrid) and were tested with 45 people with different cognitive impairments (mainly Down syndrome). These experiments are described in detail in the deliverable *D2.3 Dissemination Results 1*.

3 BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE FRANCE (ORT)

3.1 ACTIVITY

A stand for a 3-day-participation at the Education Fair in Paris and a 1 hour conference on Beaconing.

3.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

Beaconing platform and ecosystem, authoring tool and mini-games.

3.3 STAKEHOLDERS

Teachers at secondary school and VET and university, training directors, business developers, representatives, marketing directors, ministry of education, digital learning managers.

3.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

150 during the conference, around 8000 participants to the fair.

3.5 CONTEXT

The presentation of Beaconing Ecosystem (from the R&D to the Pilot perspectives) at a conference organized by ORT that gathered around 150 attendees from the Educational sectors and also during the 3 days of the Fair , at the dedicated stand Beaconing was showcased to teachers, Educational professionals, Education networks (such as Canope , Espe, CRI...) that were later engaged to promote the beaconing solution. This fair attracts all education professionals in France.

3.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

Posts on twitter on @educatectice, @beaconingeu, @minedu accounts that have around 15000 followers, advertisement of Beaconing on the fair website (http://www.educatec-educatice.com/exposant_397_5297_p.html?eid=11323) and on Ort Innovation website.

3.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

During the fair, we prepared Brochures and Small posters in French to be distributed. And we had 2 laptops computer (one for teachers side and one for student side) with the Beaconing platform to demonstrate and we also printed out QRcodes to launch a geolocalised quest done for the purpose of the EDUCATEC Fair:

<https://atcc.beaconing.eu/app.php?game=359&device=browser#modal0>

This quest has been trialed by 45 users.

Also, following those events, we produced tutorials both by video and by writing, that can be reached here:

User manual Beaconing : Créer sa quête gamifiée géolocalisée : <http://beaconing.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Beaconing-ORT-Manuel-Utilisateur-V1.1.pdf>

3.8 OTHER INFORMATION

- Photos of the conference below, showing the huge success, around 150 participants to the conference, 8000 visitors and around 300 persons coming to our stand during the 3 days.
- The event was disseminated through different media: twitter, Facebook.
- Follow-up activities: description of any other related activity originated from this one
- A large and diverse public were attracted, the conference can easily be in French and/or English, as there were no language issues.

Figure 1. Pictures of participants at fair Educatec Educative for digital and innovative education (France).

Figure 2. Tweets of BEACONING presentation at fair Educatec Educative for digital and innovative education (France).

Figure 3. Tweets about the fair Educatec Educatice for digital and innovative education (France).

Official invitation sent:

As announced, ORT will be attending the three days (15-17th Nov) to the EDUCATICE Fair (for educational professional) in Paris.

We will be more than happy if you want to meet us on the Hall7.1 of Portes de Versailles Expo, where we have reserved a booth there to showcase Beaconing to the Educational stakeholders.

We will also present Beaconing Ecosystem on the 15th of November in a conference, from 2PM to 3PM, dedicated to educational stakeholders; and our expert On Gamification, Pervasiveness, Mr Sylvester Arnab, will present the Beaconing basements to the audience.

For that purpose, we've created a geolocalised challenge around Porte de Versailles that can be played flashing that QR CODE:

Following to that EVENT, we were invited by :

The French ESPE Network on the 2-3 Feb: <http://beaconing.eu/fr/beaconin-presentation-au-reseau-espe-paris/>

Figure 4. French ESPE Network.

The French CANOPE Educational Network during 2 workshops :

<https://medium.com/@Orme2/la-ludification-en-m%C3%A9diation-4485bfc6657b>

Marseille: <http://beaconing.eu/events/beaconing-presentation-and-hands-on-workshops-in-marseille-with-canope-network/> for which a dedicated geolocalised quest has been created for engaging attendees (around 100 persons) to go by walk from the Canope premise to the Bibliothèque 13 premise during the break: The quest <https://atcc.beaconing.eu/app.php?game=755> has been played by 45 users :

Figure 5. The French CANOPE Educational Network.

In the afternoon, an hands-on workshop was organized aiming at providing early access to stakeholders to the Beaconing geolocalised authoring tool

Manosque: <http://beaconing.eu/events/beaconing-presentation-participation-at-a-round-table-and-hands-on-workshop-in-manosque/>

In which Beaconing was presented to the attendees (around 70 teachers from the region of PACA in France), followed by a hands-on workshop in the afternoon aiming at providing early access to stakeholders to the Beaconing geolocalised authoring tool.

Figure 6. Hands-on workshop at The French CANOPE Educational Network.

And we launched a series of Webinars both in French and English: <http://beaconing.eu/fr/webinaire-le-20-ou-le-21-fevrier-prochain-pour-apprendre-a-cree-des-learning-experiences-gamifiees-et-geolocalisees/> that gathered around 40 attendees training them to practise with the Beaconing solution.

4 BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE ROMANIA (SIVECO)

4.1 ACTIVITY

Running 4 workshops in schools with teachers and students in order to present and test the Beaconing project developed tools.

We presented:

- User interface,
- Authoring tool,
- Meta-game,
- Minigames
- Example of scenario

We also sent, after the workshop, the links of the tools in order to collect a more accurate feedback.

Survey link, provided by BIBA, to be completed by the participants after covering the tools presented.

All the participants were pleased with the tools presented and they are eager to see them in the final version and to start the large scale pilot.

We really need user guidelines for all the tools that they will use.

4.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

During this workshops we presented to the participants:

- The project platform;
- The meta-game;
- The Authoring Tool;
- Serious games

4.3 STAKEHOLDERS

The main stakeholders involved in the activity are schools, teachers and students.

4.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

SIVECO experts participated at 2 sessions with teachers and students at “Grigore Moisil” National College, Bucharest, “Saint Mary” Special Middle School for Hearing Impaired, Bucharest and another 2 sessions on-line.

At the 1st session from “Grigore Moisil” National College, 22 teachers and 7 students participated from the following schools:

- “Grigore Moisil” National College, Bucharest
- High School “William Shakespeare”, Timisoara
- National College Grigore Moisil, Timisoara
- High School “Aurel Lazar”
- National College “Mircea cel Batran”
- Technical College Energetic
- National College “Stefan Odobleja”, Craiova

- High School Videle

At the 2nd session from “Saint Mary” Special Middle School for Hearing Impaired, 8 teachers participated from the following schools

- Saint Mary” Special Middle School for Hearing Impaired
- National Vocational College “Nicolae Titulescu” Slatina, Olt
- Technological High School “Virgil Madgearu”, Rosiorii de Vede, Teleorman
- High School “Aurel Lazar”

At 3rd and 4th online sessions , 14 teachers and 35 students participated from the following schools:

- Technical College “Mihai Bravu”, Bucharest
- National College “Grigore Moisil”, Bucharest
- Technical Energetic College, Constanta
- High School "Aurel Lazar"
- National College “Mihai Eminescu”, Satu Mare
- National Vocational College "Nicolae Titulescu", Slatina
- High School “William Shakespeare”, Timisoara
- High School Videle
- Saint Mary” Special Middle School for Hearing Impaired

4.5 CONTEXT

Presenting the developed tools within Beaconing project, tools that will be used by the teachers and students in piloting stage.

4.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

Posts on twitter ([@BeaconingEU](#) [#STEM](#) [#seriousgames](#)).

Also, 29 more schools were reached and are on a waiting list.

4.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

Dissemination of the event among schools, laptop/desktop available in the meeting room, internet connection, projector.

4.8 OTHER INFORMATION

In January 2018 new workshops will follow with teachers and students in order to collect new feedback and hopefully succes stories.

Figure 7. Pictures of workshops in schools with teachers and students (Romania).

5 GAME AUTHORIZING TOOL BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE PORTUGAL (INESC TEC)

5.1 ACTIVITY

The activity consisted of two game jams focused on developing narratives that take advantage of the location of the player to provide learning.

The first part consisted of a workshop focused on instructing attendees on how to use Beaconing's authoring tool to build a narrative-based sequence of challenges that supported learning activities while walking the streets of the city center of Porto. As a result, each group of participants was able to create a location-based narrative that challenged players to solve mini-games in distinct locations of the city.

The software was disclosed as a simple application that required no programming skills, and attendees were only required to bring an Android smartphone, to select a learning topic and to create a narrative that took place in Porto.

In the second part of the event, participants travelled outside to test and experience their creations, only to return for informal discussion and feedback, providing information on design, workflow logic and usability of the authoring tool.

5.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

Authoring tool.

5.3 STAKEHOLDERS

The main stakeholders involved in the activity were schools, students, and media labs.

5.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/ COMPANIES/ PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

The first event involved PhD students (about 12) of the Doctoral Program in Digital Media and occurred during the event Creative Colab 17.

The second event involved a random sample of subjects, but mainly higher education students with many attending their first year (about 20), during the Future Places 2017: Media Lab for Citizenship, an international open event.

The first occurred at the Faculty of Engineering and the second at the Media Innovation Labs, both at the University of Porto.

5.5 CONTEXT

This activity was focused on the design, workflow logic and usability of the authoring tool. The main goals of this activity were to:

1. Analyse the workflow logic of interaction with the tool;
2. Analyse its capabilities to create linear and non-linear learning paths;
3. Obtain feedback on the usability of the authoring tool;
4. Analyse the experience of geolocated games.

5.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

The events/ experiments gained coverage in the media, including:

- Journal and media websites:
 - <http://futureplaces.org/labs/beaconing/>
- Publications on the original game validation experiments:
 - Master thesis: João Miguel Polónia Pascoal Faria, Pervasive Games for Education, Mestrado Integrado em Engenharia Informática e Computação, FEUP, 2017. <http://hdl.handle.net/10216/106178>

5.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

To be reproduced in a different country or context, the authoring tool only needs to support different languages; however, English was used instead of Portuguese in these events.

6 VET BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE UK (HWU)

6.1 ACTIVITY

This activity consists of a series of workshops in vocational education and training (VET) colleges in Scotland, with students and teachers to promote the adoption of gamified learning and to test the technologies for anywhere, anytime learning. The students conducted the gamified learning in a class and in the workshops. These trials also provide information on the applicability and perception of games as an educational tool to promote discussion and reflection in the classroom.

6.2 BEACONING AND SCOTTISH QUALIFICATIONS AUTHORITY

BEACONING VET-game SQA requirements

BEACONING VET-game is to ensure students understand the importance of workplace activities with respect to their vocational trade, in this case stonemasonry. The game has been developed by Imaginary SRL, who is also a partner in Beaconing project. The choice of game was driven by the Scottish Vocational Qualifications (SVQs) and other SQA accredited qualifications. SVQs are based upon national standards, and provide evidence that learners can do their jobs well. Studied in the workplace, in college or with training providers, SVQs are available in many subject areas that cover STEM. The VET-game is intended for SVQ Level 3 (SCQF Level 6 & 7) onwards with students typically from 16 years onwards.

6.3 STAKEHOLDERS

The main stakeholders involved in the activity are VET colleges, teachers, students and educational authorities.

6.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

We have contacted Edinburgh College³ and City of Glasgow College in Scotland⁴ to increase the exposure of the VET-game. Both colleges conduct stonemasonry courses and are the leading colleges in this sector.

Outreach collaboration has also been established with the CyberBuild Lab⁵ in Serious Games and different levels of immersive reality continuums to support the construction industry. There is communications with the Construction Industry Training Board (CITB)⁶, which is UK's Industry Training Board for the construction industry and a partner in ConstructionSkills, the Sector Skills Council, devoted to building competitive advantage for the construction industry and the people who work in it.

The goal is to reach as many stonemasonry education and training institutes. It should be noted that a cohort of 15-20 students per year is considered very large in stonemasonry. As of this writing (December 2017) 2 colleges with a total of 6 teachers have participated in examining the perception and applicability of the VET-game. A total of 30 teachers and

³ www.edinburghcollege.ac.uk/

⁴ <https://www.cityofglasgowcollege.ac.uk/>

⁵ cyberbuild.hw.ac.uk/

⁶ <https://www.citb.co.uk/>

professionals for the Dutch vocational education sector were also introduced to the VET-game when they visited The City of Glasgow college. Initial experiments of the game with 17 students from 2 schools were carried out, validating the game itself and basic analytics collection.

The colleges and teachers have already been contacted for further experiments. As of November 2017, they have confirmed their participation. It is intended in May 2018 to conduct further trials with the improved version of the VET-game

6.5 CONTEXT

This activity focuses on the applicability of desktop and wearable technologies for use by teachers and students to understand different stonemasonry processes and SQA requirements. The main goals of this activity are to:

1. Increase the adoption of digitalised connected game-based learning in schools
2. Involve teachers in the application of new pedagogical technologies in schools
3. Analyse the use and acceptability by teachers and students of the Beaconing platform

As the game structure is general, the results are applicable to both BEACONING and non-project games that have highly physical-virtual inter-activeness.

The trial on the wearable technology was to establish the acceptability and the uptake of connected systems able to provide objective analytics of learning and competency gained. The gradient scoring method proposed is applicable to future cyber-physical based education technology, particularly where learning is happening in the workplace and the transition of learning from classroom to the workplace.

6.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

HWU has been invited to a Commissioning meeting with CITB (Construction Industry Training Board) worth £1.5M from the UK Government. HWU has also been invited to showcase its Hololens VET-game developments at an international technology event (<https://www.wearable-technologies.eu/>) in Munich, January 2018. VET-game will validation experiments gained significant coverage in the media, including:

- Publications:
 - o Sivanathan, A., Mcgibbon, S., Lim, T., Ritchie, J., & Abdel-Wahab, M. (2017, August). A Cyber-Physical Gaming System for Vocational Training. In ASME 2017 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference (pp. V001T02A063-V001T02A063). American Society of Mechanical Engineers.
 - o Read, A., Ritchie, J., & Lim, T. (2016, August). A UNITY Sketch Based Modelling Environment for Virtual Assembly and Machining to Evaluate DFMA Metrics. In ASME 2016 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference (pp. V01BT02A049-V01BT02A049). American Society of Mechanical Engineers.
 - o Brock, A., Lim, T., Ritchie, J. M., & Weston, N. (2016, August). Context-Aware Content Generation for Virtual Environments. In ASME 2016 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference (pp. V01BT02A045-V01BT02A045). American Society of Mechanical Engineers.

- Hauge, J. M. B., Lim, T., Kalverkamp, M., Haase, F., & Bellotti, F. (2016, August). Analysis on Educating Mechanical Engineers Through Serious Games Using Pervasive Technologies. In ASME 2016 International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference (pp. V01BT02A050-V01BT02A050). American Society of Mechanical Engineers.

6.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

To be reproduced in a different country or context, the VET-game should be integrated with the BEACONING platform and its tools. The topic addressed by the game would be of interest to the schools and educational authorities seeking advancement in mixed reality learning environments.

Beyond that, the VET-game could be used in any other country / context. The non-reliance on textural schemes brings a host of advantages from the perspective of languages. Additionally, dashboards would require a minimum configuration to visualise and track progress.

6.8 OTHER INFORMATION

The trails are built on top of a previous experience for cyber-physical systems and body area networks used in training and human factors logging for Scottish Water and the production of training material and understanding the associated ergonomics for stonemasonry.

7 CO-DESIGNING PLAY-LESSON PATHS WITH THE BEACONING LEARNING TAXONOMY - BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE UK (COVUNI)

7.1 ACTIVITY

All the teachers from a local primary school in Coventry (Howes Primary) participated in a full-day workshop aimed at introducing them to game based learning design, and to the Beaconing conceptual and pedagogical architecture.

This started with a presentation and discussion of the underlying theory of game based learning and game design based learning, then moved to a hands-on game prototyping exercise based on modifying known games toward obtaining the intended learning outcomes.

Having done this, participants were introduced to the basic concepts of pervasive gaming, and were introduced to the Beaconing Learning Taxonomy as a useful tool to scaffold the creation of pervasive game scenarios.

In the conclusive activity of the day, the participants used all the knowledge and processes discussed and experienced throughout the day to create a number of Beaconing Missions, closely connected to the local learning opportunities of Coventry, and even to connect them into a non-linear and interlinked Gamified Lesson Paths.

7.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

The Beaconing taxonomy was used for developing lesson paths. Mini games, the location-based component and the authoring tool were introduced to the teachers.

7.3 STAKEHOLDERS

The participants in the workshops were 12 primary school teachers, plus the headmaster. While elementary schools are in general outside the scope of Beaconing, Howes Elementary has an excellent portfolio of STEM education as part of the Scientix and VEX robotics networks, therefore constituting an optimal testbed for both grounding the conceptual pedagogical innovations that are integral part of the Beaconing project, and for envisioning future extensions of it.

7.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

12 teachers (and the Headmaster) from 1 primary school.

7.5 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

The workshop helped these already technologically savvy teachers to take a further step and focus on the co-design of interactive activities with their students. In particular, it enabled us to provide an initial, grounded validation of the Learning Taxonomy, and to establish an ongoing collaboration with a relevant local partner (see also follow-up activities).

7.6 CONTEXT

The activity was a full day workshop, framed as professional development for the participants, and carried out in the Disruptive Media Learning Lab of Coventry University, a versatile space designed to foster an informal and collaborative approach to teaching & learning.

7.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

While the aforementioned space is specifically designed to be conducive for this kind of creative and collaborative activity, the overall workshop could be easily reproduced, as it is, by choice, completely paper based, so as to enable even less tech savvy participants to fully engage with the underlying process.

It is however very important that the facilitator has a sound knowledge of the landscape of game based learning and game design (to properly scaffold the participants in moving their first active steps), and an in-depth understanding of the Beaconing Learning Taxonomy.

7.8 OTHER INFORMATION

- **Media content:**

Figure 8. Pictures from the workshop in a local primary school in Coventry to introduce game based learning design and BEACONING conceptual and pedagogical architecture.

- **Follow-up activities:**

From this initial workshop an ongoing collaboration has been established with Howes Primary, which will work with Coventry University and Coventry University College to further validate the Beaconing Platform, now moving from a paper based creative workshop to actual engagement with the online platform.

- **Lessons learned:**

This workshop validated the Learning Taxonomy as a functional scaffolding tool for teachers, even if at a level that is different from the general Beaconing scope, as the participants were easily able (after being provided with the appropriate conceptual tools through appropriate but brief training) to work within the framing provided, which in turn supported creativity and ease of formalization. This provides us with two main insights:

- 1) The Learning Taxonomy is a valuable play/learning design tool, though of course it will be further iterated through the pilots.
- 2) Teachers work at their best when provided with a broad training (but still brief), not only on the Beaconing platform, but on the general principles of game based learning design.

8 ITALY BEST PRACTICE EVENT – MILAN SMALL SCALE PILOT (IMAGINARY)

8.1 ACTIVITY

On November 30th, 2017 in Sesto San Giovanni, a small city close to Milan, the Beaconing project has been piloted at I.I.S. "Enrico De Nicola" technical and artistic high school.

One classroom of students was engaged for nearly 3 hours with the Beaconing's treasure hunt game in chasing clues and quests prepared by their teachers.

The treasure hunt game has been organized inside the school's building and players have been provided with the location based component linked to a set of STEM mini games.

Students, bringing their own device (BYOD approach) and split in 4 small groups, had to follow the clues triggered by each successfully completed mini game to reach the prize that their teachers prepared for the winner team.

It was really impressive the players' engagement in solving as quick as possible the math and physics challenges prepared by their teachers in order to reach the end of the path sooner than their mates.

The perceived feeling is that this kind of activity represented really a fun and engaging innovation both for students and teachers not used in experiencing the school duties in a such funny way.

At the end of the game was also exploited the pilot event to perform some short interviews with some students to collect their feelings and feedback about the Beaconing experience.

The output of this event is available in the following video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bPDG0jY1oiQ>

8.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

Mini games, location based component, authoring tool and the learning analytics platform.

8.3 STAKEHOLDERS

Students and their teachers from I.I.S. "Enrico De Nicola" technical and artistic high school.

8.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

This event engaged two classes of students belonging to the 3rd year of the high school for a total amount of 24 players and 2 teachers.

8.5 CONTEXT

The context for this event was an half day of Beaconing's treasure hunt indoor activities performed inside the I.I.S. "Enrico De Nicola" high school.

IMA's staff coached the teachers before the event on how to assist the teams during the game and prepared some paper material to foster and enhance the "gamified" approach of the experience (e.g. paper leaderboard, paper badges with the team logo and the player's name).

8.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

A derived impact for this kind of activity is to leverage on the pilot activity to record and edit a video to be used to document and disseminate the Beaconing experience using an engaging media such as the videos.

Figure 9. Pictures from the small scale pilot in a high school in Milan.

8.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

To be able to reproduce this experience partners have to record small video snippets and take pictures during the game play and (if possible) to record some short interviews to students or teachers asking about how the experience was and put all together in a short video (up to 3 minutes length) to be shared on social networks. The recording of the interviews and the texts present in the video can be in the original language of the country where the event takes place, then the final video can be subtitled directly on Youtube.

9 ITALY BEST PRACTICE EVENT – MILAN TREASURE HUNT GAME ON ADDICTIONS PREVENTION (IMAGINARY)

9.1 ACTIVITY

Participation to the “*International Day Against Drug Abuse and Illicit Trafficking*” (<http://www.un.org/en/events/drugabuseday/>) on 2018 June the 26th, with a treasure hunt game in Milan (Italy) dedicated to students (Target: 1st and 2nd classes of high school) organized in collaboration with Società Italiana Tossicodipendenze (www.sitd.it). The goal is to raise awareness in teenagers about addictions’ risks, engaging them in a location based activity in their town. Such event is supposed to raise a big impact in terms of dissemination and communication from all the local media connected to this international day event. The institution that will be organizing the event operates in tight collaboration with Regione Lombardia, this means that this event is supposed to be the first of a series of similar events organized in the future in collaboration with Regione Lombardia using the same approach but addressing different use cases related to the health topic.

9.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

Mini games, location based component, authoring tool and the learning analytics platform.

9.3 STAKEHOLDERS

Teenagers and their parents, social health institutions belonging to the Milan district (ASL, ASST) local media and local newspapers.

9.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

Regione Lombardia, Società Italiana Tossicodipendenze (www.sitd.it)

9.5 CONTEXT

The pedagogical content will be provided to IMA by SITD and IMA will create the treasure hunt game narrative and mini games. The web link to the game will be provided to the participants through social media events creation and fliers distribution. Teenagers and their parents will have the opportunity to access the game using their own device (BYOD approach) with no special requirements in terms of HW and SW specifications.

9.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

The expected impact of this event is very high since it will be held within the context of the International Day Against Drug Abuse and Illicit Trafficking so we expect local institutions such as Regione Lombardia, Società Italiana Tossicodipendenze and the local health authority actively support the event with press releases, social media communications and onsite presence during the event.

9.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENTE COUNTRY/CONTEXT

To reproduce such event in other country the recommendation is to select an International Day or a big local event supposed to raise high attention by the local media and the citizens and organize a treasure hunt game using Beaconing mini game with the goal to raise awareness or assess knowledge about the specific topic addressed by the event. To maximize the impact,

Success cases from BEACONING

the active engagement of the local authorities that support the event, is more than recommended.

10 BEACONING SCIENTIX COLLABORATION – BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE FRANCE (ORT)

10.1 ACTIVITY

A plenary conference and a Workshop session to Scientix Ambassadors in FCL, in Brussels, during the 17th Science Projects Workshop in the Future Classroom Lab (SPW@FCL), Scientix.

10.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

Beaconing platform and ecosystem, authoring tool and mini-games.

10.3 STAKEHOLDERS

Teachers at primary, secondary school, Scientix AMBASSADORS.

10.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS INVOLVED

45 during the conference, 12 participants to the workshop.

10.5 CONTEXT

The presentation of Beaconing at the conference was made at the **17th Science Projects Workshop in the Future Classroom Lab (SPW@FCL), organized by Scientix**, for digital and innovative education.

10.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

Posts on twitter, advertisement of Beaconing on the event website (<http://www.scientix.eu/spw17-at-fcl-after>). The Twitter account #SPW17 reported the event and the courses about beaconing presentation was given to the 45 Scientix Ambassadors from different EU countries on the 18th of November. Further to that short introduction ORT conducted a Webinar session with 15 teachers recorded .

10.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

Brochures to be distributed, laptops with the Beaconing platform to demonstrate, Presentation. A ready to run Geolocalised quest to be done in the location of your event: printing out Qrcodes to simulate the fact that end-users are moving from a Point Of Interest to another (as usually end-users are not willing to get out with their mobiles).

10.8 OTHER INFORMATION

- Website of Scientix: <http://www.scientix.eu/spw17-at-fcl-after>

If you look for the hashtag #spw17 you can see what happened this weekend, for example: <https://twitter.com/search?f=tweets&vertical=default&q=%23spw17&src=typd>

Figure 10. Scientix webpage with post about the 17th Science Projects workshop.

Figure 11. Pictures from the 17th Science Projects workshop.

11 BEACONING WEBINARS – BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE FRANCE (ORT)

11.1 ACTIVITY

Webinars organized both in English and French to showcase the Beaconing Ecosystem and engage stakeholders. Different webinars have been conducted both in English and in French with contacted stakeholders during the events (Educative, Scientix Ambassadors, ESPE teachers, Canope Event); The webinars have been recorded live and have been later distributed to participants and new comers.

11.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

Beaconing platform and ecosystem, authoring tool and mini-games.

11.3 STAKEHOLDERS

Teachers at primary, secondary school, Scientix AMBASSADORS.

11.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

50 persons during the webinars.

11.5 CONTEXT

The webinar Beaconing at the conference was made on the 19th of December, the 17th of January, the 18th of January, the 25th of January, the 23 and 24 the of March.

After the webinar, the participants have received an email like that one below:

“Dear Beaconing Webinar attendees,

Thanks for participating on January 18th to the Beaconing Webinar.

We ‘ve attendees from different EU countries (That’s Europe) and that was with great pleasure for me and my colleague to showcase the Beaconing ecosystem to all of you.

You can find the powerpoint presentation of the Beaconing Webinar https://1drv.ms/p/s!AoW_zOSmslaBg9EriwYESOFawjbrHQ and you can view the Beaconing ecosystem demo video at that link : <http://beaconing.paris.ort.asso.fr/VIDEO/beaconing%20DEMO%20FULL%20GAME.mp4>

Also, if you’ve missed the begining of the Webinar, you can find the recording of the live session here : <https://meet12407274.adobeconnect.com/pl04qc74mzde/>

To receive your credentials for accessing the Beaconing Ecosystem, please fill-in first that questionnaire <https://survey.biba-gaminglab.com/survey/index.php?p=survey&survey=5&groups=75>

and you’ll receive the credentials for accessing the platform. In the survey, please to the question : “Please name the Workshop ID:” write : “ORT your Name”

Also, you can find more information on the Beaconing Website <http://beaconing.eu> and a Beaconing video here : <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dJA7ohE9X8g>

All the Best from Beaconing board,

And Happy to be on the way of Beaconing Ambassadors!”

11.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

Posts on twitter on the ScientixEU network were made relaying the event on the Beaconing Website, advertisement of Beaconing on the beaconing.EU website and also on the ORT EDLAB website: <http://edlab.paris.ort.asso.fr/edlab> including registration forms.

11.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCES IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

Presentation, Video Recording of a session. We conducted the webinars using a Adobe Connect solution that can have up to 100 participants to the meeting and recording facilities. A powerpoint presentation was prepared: https://1drv.ms/p/s!AoW_zOSmslaBg9EriwYESOFawjbrHQ

A running Beaconng platform, with a preset GLP need to be defined to run the demo.

11.8 OTHER INFORMATION

- Twitter/Facebook/ <http://edlab.paris.ort.asso.fr/2017/12/05/1801-beaconing-create-and-share-your-gamified-lesson-paths-2pm-4pm-cet/>

Figure 12. Screen captures of the Beaconing webinar by ORT.

12 BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE TURKEY (SEBIT)

12.1 ACTIVITY

Engaging and Educational Gamified-Lesson Plan creation with head teachers (in two workshops) and with subject teachers (in two schools).

Mission-Quest structure or any other game mechanics do not guarantee an engaging experience or even play. Similarly, some quiz test activity or other mini games do not guarantee educational value or even learning.

Designing GLPs on BEACONING is not a trivial matter. It is a trial & error process itself; not only for teachers who attend the workshops, but also professional instructional designers in SEBIT. The two authoring tools of BEACONING (putting the narrative authoring tool aside) are powerful tools, but to use them effectively and to create engaging learning experiences in STEM topics is a trial & error learning process. Therefore, we devote time with our volunteer teachers to develop best practices for creating GLPs.

12.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

Beaconing platform and ecosystem; in particular i) Authoring Tool ii) Context Aware Challenges Authoring Tool.

12.3 STAKEHOLDERS

Teachers at secondary schools, instructional designers, educational coordinators, headmasters, ministry of education, digital learning managers.

12.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

A total of 150 head teachers in two workshops and 10 subject teachers in two schools.

12.5 CONTEXT

SEBIT's first responsibility is to run large scale pilots and that relies on the quality of GLPs which will be presented to the 70K+ students who use SEBIT's private schools platform VCloud. Therefore, it is critical to develop best practices of creating GLPs.

12.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

A number of impact areas can be identified: i) preparing training material and user guides for the authoring tools ii) quality GLPs to be taken to the large scale pilots, iii) engaging head teachers who can train other teachers iv) gaining experience on using BEACONING platform and discovering its limits and affordances inform exploitation plans and activities.

12.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

Best Practices in creating quality (engaging and educational) GLPs is planned to turn into user manuals and training materials so that other teachers and/or instructional designers can also create quality GLPs or reuse/repurpose the existing ones effectively.

12.8 OTHER INFORMATION

- Photos of the two workshops

Figure 13. Introducing BEACONING to Turkish head teacher

Figure 14. Hands-on GLP design trials by Turkish Head Teachers

13 BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE: CROSS EUROPEAN LOCATION-BASED EVENT (GEOMOTION GAMES)

13.1 ACTIVITY

Geomotion Games have led the organization of a cross European location-based game. The event takes advantage of the geolocation technologies developed in the project by Geomotion Games to create a playful urban experience in which young citizens from all over the European continent participate in a collaborative location-based game on the same day and at the same time while discovering their city and learning STEM skills.

The purpose of the event was to bring together young people from all over the European continent on the same day and at the same time in a fun urban gamified experience in which collaboration and the discovery of context become a key aspect of the game.

Objectives & Outcomes

- Engage local stakeholders in the participation of outdoor educational activities through ICT.
- Create an educational location-based game using BEACONING technologies that can be played on the same day and same time.
- Encourage learning and discovery of the cities through games and gamification.
- Promote the BEACONING Project and context-aware technologies applied to education and STEM skills development.
- Location-based game to be played in 16 European cities.

Event Day: 10th February 2018

Event Time: from 10h to 20h (CEST time)

13.1.1 The Game

Summary of the experience

The Earth Special Agency have discovered that a mysterious tycoon called “Ulrik Morgan” runs a double-sided private corporation. Publicly it is dedicated to the research and development on sustainable energies and technologies. But it’s been leaked that this corporation have a network of secret installations where is hiding toxic products with which they really make profits illegally.

Several informants from the Earth Special Agency have collected 4 parts of the map that will guide agents to the clandestine underground facilities. But they cannot be together in the city because of security reasons.

Participants will need to access the treasure-hunt game through their smartphones, find the informants hidden in the city, demonstrate their knowledge on energy & environment and unlock the clues to uncover their exact locations in the city to finally find the hidden facilities, unmask the bad guy and save the environment.

Game Time: 120m

Game Type: Treasure Hunt

Game Theme: Energy & the Environment

13.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

Context Aware Challenges Authoring Tool.

13.3 STAKEHOLDERS

- Students at secondary schools.
- Teachers at secondary schools.
- Families and youngsters between 12 and 16 years old.
- Local partners: each project partner linked with local partners, both to drive the advertising and for charitable ends. Total local partners engaged: 9.

13.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

- 450 users have participated.
- Cities around the World: 17 cities.
- Local Partners engaged: 9 partners
- Find below partners involved and local partners engaged in each city:

Country	City	Local Partner
UK	Coventry	Coventry City Libraries Fab Lab City of Culture bid
UK	Haywards Heath	Burgess Hill School for Girls Burgess Hill Academy Armstrongs Opticians
SPAIN	Madrid	
SPAIN	Barcelona	Urban explorer
FRANCE	Paris	ORT and EdFab
FRANCE	Montreuil	ORT and EdFab
FRANCE	Strasbourg	ORT
FRANCE	Marseille	ORT
FRANCE	Toulouse	ORT
FRANCE	Lyon	ORT
TURKEY	Ankara	TEMA

- Some of the Facebook Events created:

- IMAGINARY - Milano (Italy):
<https://www.facebook.com/events/1526647120759409/>
- COVENTRY UNI - Coventry (UK):
<https://www.facebook.com/events/1846432105656160/>
- HANDS FREE COMPUTING - Haywards Heath (UK):
<https://www.facebook.com/events/1607638835981480/>
- GEOMOTION GAMES: <https://www.facebook.com/events/571887463152535/>
- BIBA: <https://www.facebook.com/events/1760030027374971/>

13.5 CONTEXT

Geomotion Games is responsible for developing the Context Aware Challenges Authoring tool to create educational location-based games. As a location-based gaming industry leader Geomotion took the lead to coordinate the creation of this event.

13.6 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

A number of impact areas can be identified:

- i) Creating a location-based game that needs to be repurposed in each city.
- ii) Testing Context Aware Challenges Authoring Tool.
- iii) Testing location-based game experience and technology.

13.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

Best Practices in creating quality (engaging and educational) location-based games that can be repurposed only changing the Points of Interest but keeping the same narrative that engages users across different countries and cultures.

13.8 OTHER INFORMATION

- Pictures of the experience in different locations:

Figure 15. Pictures from the event in Barcelona (Spain)

Figure 16. Pictures from the event in Ankara (Turkey)

Figure 17. Picture from the event in Paris (France)

Figure 18. Promotional materials for the event

14 CO-DESIGNING LOCATION BASED GAMES FOR USERS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS - BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE UK (COVUNI)

14.1 ACTIVITY

Students from the Coventry University Therapeutic Orticulture module have engaged with the Consortium to co-design a pervasive game experience that is aimed at supporting students from a special needs school to both explore STEM (natural science and math related contents) and experience an increased autonomy as learning. This translated into the co-design of a nature-oriented treasure hunt location based game.

14.2 BEACONING AND THIRD-PARTY PRODUCTS INVOLVED

Location based authoring tool.

14.3 STAKEHOLDERS

The participants in the workshops were Therapeutic orticulture University students, and students from a primary special needs school.

14.4 NUMBER OF PEOPLE/COMPANIES/PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS DIRECTLY INVOLVED

4 Therapeutic orticulture University Students teachers and 20 special needs primary school students.

14.5 IMPACT OR RELEVANCE

The workshop helped us as co-designers to ensure that the Beaconing Location Based Authoring tool can be deployed as a pedagogical design tool even with scarcely technologically literate users. It also enabled to run a basic usability check, and to establish an ongoing collaboration with relevant local partners.

14.6 CONTEXT

The activity was a series of tutorials, where we supported the students from the Therapeutic Orticulture module in designing a location based game aimed at enabling and supporting children with special needs to explore and appreciate a natural environment. The actual activity with the children was run in an enclosed nature park, therefore ensuring the safety and controlled conditions of the experience.

14.7 REQUIREMENTS TO BE REPRODUCED IN A DIFFERENT COUNTRY/CONTEXT

The co-design experience does not require anything specific, aside from a sound knowledge of the functions of the authoring tool and a willingness to engage in co-design.

The co-designed nature trail itself could easily be adapted to any similar park or nature-oriented context, although the difficulty of the challenges should probably be raised were it to be used with different audiences.